

Organ-specific isoform selection of fatty acid binding proteins in tissue-resident lymphocytes

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One Sentence Summary:

Tissue-resident cells exhibit tissue-specific overlays to the T_{RM} cell residency program that includes flexible FABP isomer selection tailored to the tissue of lodgment.

Abstract

Tissue-resident memory T (T_{RM}) cells exist throughout the body where they are poised to mediate local immune responses. Although studies have defined a common mechanism of residency independent of location, there is likely to be a level of specialization that adapts T_{RM} cells to their given tissue of lodgment. It has been shown that T_{RM} cells in the skin rely on the uptake of exogenous fatty acids for their survival and upregulate fatty acid binding proteins (FABP) 4 and FABP 5 as part of their transcriptional program. However, FABPs exist as a larger family of isoforms with different members selected in a tissue-specific fashion that is optimized for local fatty acid availability. Here we show that although T_{RM} cells in a range of tissue widely express FABPs, they are not restricted to FABP 4 and 5. Instead, T_{RM} cells show varying patterns of isoform usage that are determined by tissue-derived factors. These patterns are malleable since T_{RM} cells relocated to different organs modify their FABP expression in line with their new location. As a consequence, these results argue for tissue-specific overlays to the T_{RM} cell residency program, including FABP expression that is tailored to the particular tissue of T_{RM} cell lodgment.

Introduction

Memory T cells are generated by infection and provide enhanced immune responses on pathogen re-encounter. Whilst memory T cells that circulate via the blood play a key role in the secondary response (1) it has become increasingly clear that T cells found in non-lymphoid tissues are critical for early infection control especially for pathogens that enter the body using these compartments (2-6). Some of the peripheral memory T cells permanently reside within the tissues and these are now known as tissue-resident memory T (T_{RM}) cells. T_{RM} cell development involves a cascade of transcriptional changes, which are well defined for the $CD8^+$ subset. These changes involve the engagement of a common gene expression program driven by master regulators such as members of the T-box and PRDM families, and cytokines including TGF- β (7-16). This transcriptional program results in changes critical to T cell residency, such as the downregulation of various molecules that promote tissue exit including S1P1 and CCR7, as well as upregulation of adhesion molecules critical for T cell retention and survival (8, 13, 17). Despite some redundancies and variation, this broad transcriptional program is common to T_{RM} cells from a variety of different locations and forms the foundation for tissue-residency.

Recently, it has been reported that T_{RM} cells have altered metabolic capabilities compared to circulating T cells (18-21). The latter is consistent with their long-term survival in what are often anatomically sequestered and thus potentially metabolically restrictive compartments throughout the body. In particular, Pan *et al.* have shown that T_{RM} cells in the skin upregulate the fatty acid binding protein (FABP) 4 and 5 and this alters their fatty acid uptake capabilities and long-term survival (18). However, FABPs exist as a family of different isoforms that have different fatty acid specificities. Moreover, FABPs exhibit unique patterns of tissue distribution with FABP 4 and 5 expressed abundantly in the skin (18) and differential FABP isoform expression in other tissue sites reflecting difference in local fatty acid distribution (22, 23). Thus, at the start of this investigation it remained unclear whether $CD8^+$ T_{RM} cells in tissues other than skin expressed FABPs and if so, whether expression was restricted to FABP4 and 5 or followed the tissue-specific pattern of isomer selection as seen for parenchymal cells in those locations. Here, we show that FABPs are indeed widely expressed by $CD8^+$ T_{RM} cells found in diverse organs and not by circulating memory T cells. Importantly, we found that $CD8^+$ T_{RM} cells exhibited differential

FABP isoform expression across tissues and that local environmental cues are critical to such FABP selection, not only on T_{RM} cells but also more broadly on other populations of tissue-resident immune cells.

Results

Differential expression of FABPs by T_{RM} cells in non-lymphoid organs

It has been shown that skin CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells generated in response to vaccinia virus infection express high levels of *Fabp4* and *Fabp5* (18). To determine whether this pattern of FABP expression extended to skin T_{RM} cells generated in response to a different virus, we utilized a model of HSV skin scarification (2). To this end, we transferred congenically labelled naïve CD45.1⁺ gBT-I transgenic CD8⁺ T cells that are specific for the immunodominant determinant from HSV (gB₄₉₈₋₅₀₅) into C57BL/6 mice, which were infected with HSV-1 KOS on the skin flank. By day 30 post infection (p.i.), the vast majority of CD45.1⁺ gBT-I T cells in the skin co-expressed the surface molecules CD69 and CD103 that define skin CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells in mice (2) (**Fig. 1A**). gBT-I T_{RM} cells were sorted from the skin by flow cytometry and gene expression was analyzed by quantitative (q)-PCR. Akin to those skin CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells induced by vaccinia virus (18), T_{RM} cells generated in response to HSV expressed *Fabp4* and *Fabp5* but essentially lacked expression of other FABP isoforms (**Fig. 1B**).

Given that distinct FABP isoforms are expressed by parenchymal cells in different organs (22, 23), we wanted to determine whether this paradigm extended to T_{RM} cells lodged in diverse tissues. To do this we utilized a model of lymphocytic choriomeningitis virus (LCMV) infection which results in disseminated CD8⁺ T_{RM} cell lodgment (4, 24). Naïve congenically labelled CD45.1⁺ P14 transgenic CD8⁺ T cells that are specific for LCMV (gp₃₃₋₄₁) were transferred into C57BL/6 mice, and mice were subjected to infection with LCMV Armstrong. Given the limited formation of skin T_{RM} cells after systemic LCMV infection, we enhanced skin T cell lodgment via application of the contact sensitizer 2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene (DNFB) to the skin flank 2 days p.i. (25). Gating strategies used for flow cytometric analyses are shown in **Fig. S1**. By 30 days p.i. CD45.1⁺ P14 T_{RM} cells that expressed CD69 and CD103 could be detected in the skin (skin T_{RM}) and epithelium

of the small intestine (SI-IEL T_{RM}) and P14 T_{RM} cells in the liver that lack CD103 could be identified by dual expression of CD69 and CXCR6 (**Fig. 1C**) as described (26). In this setting, FABP expression by T_{RM} cells in multiple barrier tissues could be analyzed concurrently in the same infection model. Skin P14 T_{RM} cells expressed *Fabp4* and *Fabp5* mirroring those established by HSV infection (**Fig. 1D, E**). When T_{RM} cells were isolated from the SI-IEL or liver, a different spectrum of FABP expression was observed. Of the nine known FABP isoforms investigated, liver T_{RM} cells highly expressed *Fabp1*, associated with some expression of *Fabp4* but not *Fabp5*, whereas SI-IEL T_{RM} cells expressed relatively high levels of *Fabp1*, *Fabp2* and *Fabp6* with negligible levels of *Fabp4* and *Fabp5* that are expressed by T_{RM} cells in the skin (**Fig. 1D, E**). These FABP gene expression profiles from CD8⁺ T cells residing in various organs are in line with known general tissue FABP expression patterns (22, 23). In the spleen, antigen-specific CD8⁺ naïve (T_N), central memory (T_{CM}) and effector memory (T_{EM}) cells were found not to express any FABP family members, *Fabp1-9*. Additionally, CD69⁺ antigen-specific memory CD8⁺ T cells in the spleen (spleen T_{RM}) (27) did not express any FABP genes (**Fig. 1D**). Combined, the results show that while FABP usage is a general feature of the T_{RM} cell transcriptional program, the FABP isoform selection is dictated by the local tissue environment.

Kinetics of FABP induction on T cells in non-lymphoid tissues

T_{RM} cell differentiation occurs subsequent to T cell entry into non-lymphoid tissues. We have previously shown that following HSV infection, skin-infiltrating gBT-I T cells upregulate CD69 early after skin entry, followed by expression of CD103 (8). We wanted to assess the kinetics of FABP upregulation on tissue T cells during acquisition of the tissue-resident phenotype. To do this, we followed the development of gBT-I T_{RM} cells in the skin after HSV infection, and P14 T_{RM} cells in the SI-IEL and liver following LCMV infection. The proportion of T cells expressing a tissue-resident phenotype increased over time, and by 30 days p.i. >90% of antigen-specific CD8⁺ T cells in the skin and SI-IEL showed dual expression of CD69 and CD103. Similarly, antigen-specific CD8⁺ T cells in the liver progressively increased expression of CD69 and CXCR6 following tissue entry (**Fig. 2A, B**). We next tracked changes in the expression of FABP genes as T cells progressed along the T_{RM} cell maturation pathway in the skin, SI-IEL and liver. During the effector phase of infection (7 days p.i.), we did not observe any FABP expression in CD8⁺ T cells in the spleen (**Fig. 2C**). We found that tissue-specific FABPs were upregulated in gBT-I T cells in

the skin and P14 T cells in the SI-IEL and liver, with expression following the acquisition of a tissue-resident phenotype and being highest in T_{RM} cell populations at memory time points (30 days p.i.) (Fig. 2C, D, Fig. S2). Additionally, expression kinetics were not uniform among all FABPs expressed by T_{RM} cells in a single given tissue. In SI-IEL T_{RM} cells we observed a more rapid upregulation of *Fabp1* and *Fabp2*, while *Fabp6* expression gradually increased over time (Fig. 2C, D). Note that the heatmaps in Fig. 2D depict the relative expression of each FABP isoform per row, rather than global expression. These data argue that tailored FABP expression does not occur prior to tissue-entry of antigen-specific CD8⁺ T cells but rather occurs *in situ* during resident memory T cell development, after T_{RM} cell lodgment in their tissue of residency.

Loss of FABP1 impairs the establishment of T_{RM} cells in the liver

It has been shown that T cells lacking both *Fabp4* and *Fabp5* are greatly impaired in their ability to form long-lasting T_{RM} cells in skin (18). Given the spectrum of FABP expression between different tissues, we wanted to determine whether the loss of an alternative FABP would impact T_{RM} cells in a similar fashion. T_{RM} cells in the SI-IEL and skin express multiple FABP isoforms and thus the impact of losing expression of one FABP may be compensated by other co-expressed isoforms. To this point, Pan *et al.* observed a loss of skin T cells survival in the absence of both *Fabp4* and *Fabp5*, but not cells lacking one of these isoforms (18). In contrast, FABP1 is the dominant FABP expressed by liver T_{RM} cells to such an extent that T cells lacking this isoform might be impaired to form T_{RM} cells in tissue. Using mixed bone marrow chimeras of wild-type and FABP1-deficient (*Fabp1*^{-/-}) cells that were infected with LCMV (Fig. 3A), we found such a defect of LCMV-specific (gp33⁺) T_{RM} cells in the liver, but not in populations recovered from the spleen or SI-IEL after 14 days (Fig. 3B). In separate experiments, wild-type and *Fabp1*^{-/-} CD8⁺ T cells were *in vitro* activated and transferred into mice. Such effector cell transfers intrinsically result in liver T_{RM} cell formation (35) and to lodge skin T_{RM} cells in the same mice, we treated recipients on the flank with DNFB (Fig. 3C). Consistent with our observations after LCMV infection, we found a selective loss of T_{RM} cells in the liver, but not in the spleen or skin (Fig. 3D, E). Finally, this reduction of FABP-deficient liver T_{RM} cells was restored upon re-expression of FABP1 (Fig. 3F). In these experiments, wild-type and *Fabp1*^{-/-} effector CD8⁺ T cells were transduced with either ‘empty’ (EV) or FABP1-expressing (FABP1⁺) retrovirus and cells transferred into mice. Forced expression of FABP1 in FABP1-deficient cells restored the loss of

T_{RM} cells in the liver but had no effect on splenic T cell populations (Fig. 3F). Combined, these results, demonstrate the selective reliance of T_{RM} cells on FABP expression that mirrors the dominant tissue-specific isoform usage.

FABP expression profiles are shared by diverse immune cells in the same microenvironment

We next asked if other immune cells within a given tissue also display a similar selective pattern of FABP expression to those we observed for $CD8^+$ T_{RM} cells. Tissue-residency is not just a feature of $CD8^+$ T cells but has also been described for innate lymphocytes including natural killer T (NKT) cells and innate lymphoid cells (ILC). As a group, these tissue-resident lymphocytes share common transcriptional features that promote their long-term residence (7, 28, 29). We examined FABP gene expression in endogenous immune cell populations, both tissue-resident and migratory, from the skin, SI-IEL and liver of naïve mice (Fig. S1F-H). In the skin, type-1 ILC (ILC1), dendritic epidermal T cells (DETC) and Langerhans cells (LC) expressed high levels of *Fabp4* and showed some expression of *Fabp5* when compared to naïve T cells from the spleen. In the SI-IEL, all analyzed subsets of lymphocytes isolated from the intraepithelial layer ($CD8\alpha\alpha TCR\beta$, $CD8\alpha\beta TCR\beta$, $CD8\alpha\alpha TCR\gamma\delta$ and $CD8\alpha\beta TCR\gamma\delta$) and ILC1 expressed *Fabp1*, *Fabp2* and *Fabp6* analogous to SI-IEL T_{RM} cells (Fig. 4A, B). In the liver, ILC1 expressed *Fabp1* and some *Fabp4*, and NKT cells expressed *Fabp1* and *Fabp5* (Fig. 4A, B). Tissue-specific protein expression of FABP isoforms was also verified by Western blot. We observed expression of *Fabp1* in liver-resident lymphocytes (T_{RM} , NK and NKT cells), expression of *Fabp4* and *Fabp5* by skin-resident cells (DETC) and protein expression of *Fabp1*, *Fabp2* and *Fabp6* by $CD8^+$ T cells from the SI-IEL (Fig. S3). Overall, we found that T_{RM} cells exhibited a similar pattern of FABP expression to that of other immune populations from the same tissue.

Tissue-specific cues drive FABP gene expression

Our findings that specific complements of FABP expression are induced subsequent to tissue entry and are shared by other lymphocytes within the same tissue, indicated that FABP expression is likely controlled by factors present in the local microenvironment. To test this, we examined induction of FABPs on effector $CD8^+$ T cells (which demonstrated negligible FABP expression) after culture with supernatant obtained from various tissues. To generate these supernatants, we harvested the skin, liver and spleens from naïve mice and processed these tissues into single cell

suspensions that were then cultured overnight. The following day, the supernatant from each organ culture was incubated with *in vitro* activated OT-I T cells for 24 h, after which these effector CD8⁺ T cells were assessed for changes in FABP gene expression (**Fig. 5A**). Strikingly, the supernatant harvested from liver tissue homogenates was sufficient to induce the expression of *Fabp1* in effector CD8⁺ T cells, matching the expression pattern observed in CD8⁺ T cells residing in this organ (**Fig. 5B**). Moreover, the supernatant obtained from skin tissue induced *Fabp4* expression in effector CD8⁺ T cells (**Fig. 5B**). In contrast, FABP upregulation was not observed for CD8⁺ T cells cultured with supernatant from the spleen nor in control samples where T cells were not exposed to any tissue supernatant (**Fig. 5B**). Thus, tissue-derived factors are sufficient to induce FABP expression in CD8⁺ T cells and they can dictate the FABP isoform usage in a tissue-specific fashion.

Dynamic expression of FABP genes by CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells

Tissue-resident cells show little evidence of turnover or recirculation under steady-state conditions (30-32). Yet, there is emerging evidence that following particular local challenges, skin T_{RM} cells can demonstrate functional plasticity and reprogramming (33) or can exit the tissue and give rise to new T_{RM} cell populations in downstream secondary lymphoid organs (34). This infers that although T_{RM} cells adapt to their site of residence, they may exhibit transcriptional flexibility under changing environmental circumstances. We sought to determine if established T_{RM} cell populations could reprogram their FABP expression profiles if forced to adapt to a different tissue milieu. To address this, we isolated mature populations of T_{RM} cells from the liver and transferred these cells into new recipient animals. CD69⁺CXCR6⁺ P14 T_{RM} cells were sorted from the liver of LCMV immune mice (>30 days p.i.) and liver T_{RM} cells were transferred intravenously into naïve animals that were subsequently infected with LCMV. Recipient mice were treated with the contact sensitizer DNFB on the skin flank to non-specifically recruit LCMV-primed P14 T cells into the skin (25) (**Fig. 6A**). We found that the progeny of transferred liver T_{RM} cells (ex-liver T_{RM} cells) could be recovered from tissues including the spleen, skin and SI-IEL 7 days following T_{RM} cell transfer (**Fig. 6B**). Strikingly, upon migration to new microenvironments, ex-liver T_{RM} cells changed their FABP expression profile consistent with their new tissue of lodgment. Ex-liver T_{RM} cells recovered from the skin 7 and 30 days post transfer had downregulated *Fabp1*, which was expressed by isolated liver T_{RM} cells prior to transfer, and upregulated the FABP associated with

skin residency, namely *Fabp4* (Fig. 6C). Similar site-specific changes in FABP expression were also observed in the progeny of ex-liver T_{RM} cells that migrated to the intestinal compartment, as P14 T cells isolated from the SI-IEL showed enhanced expression of *Fabp1*, *Fabp2* and *Fabp6* 30 days post transfer (Fig. 6C). These results indicated that T_{RM} cells can exhibit plasticity and adapt their FABP expression to suit new microenvironments.

Given that these experiments were performed in the context of infection with potential antigen restimulation of transferred P14 T cells, whether T_{RM} cell reactivation was required to adapt FABP expression was left unclear. To directly assess whether microenvironmental signals were sufficient for resting T_{RM} cells to change their FABP expression, we performed experiments whereby we directly transferred T_{RM} cells from one environment to another in the absence of any overt *in vivo* antigen stimulation. *In vitro* activated OT-I T cells were transferred into mice to generate liver T_{RM} cells (35) and 30 days post transfer, CD69⁺CXCR6⁺ OT-I T_{RM} cells were sorted from the liver and directly placed into the skin epidermis of naïve animals by epicutaneous transfer. In this case, we used a suspension of liver T_{RM} cells in Matrigel® Basement Membrane Matrix solution that was administered directly to abraded skin, which permits T cell entry directly into the underlying epidermis (36). Seven days post transfer, the skin was harvested and ex-liver OT-I T_{RM} cells were sorted for gene expression analysis by qPCR (Fig. 6D). We found that ex-liver OT-I T_{RM} cells placed in the skin mirrored the FABP expression of skin-resident memory T cells by downregulating *Fabp1* (expressed by liver OT-I T_{RM} cells prior to transfer) and upregulating *Fabp4* and to some extent *Fabp5* (Fig. 6E). These results demonstrate that T_{RM} cells can adapt FABP gene expression upon organ repositioning and emphasize that the local microenvironment shapes FABP isoform selection within tissues.

Discussion

Memory T cells have long been described in terms of their ability to migrate throughout the body as a surveillance mechanism against infection. However, T_{RM} cells exist as a sessile population that is particularly effective in control of tumors or pathogens in non-lymphoid environments (37). These are often sequestered locations that are distinct and highly diverse in structure, function and

general accessibility. Thus, while certain elements would be common to all tissue-resident lymphocytes, such as the shut-down of migration promoting mechanisms, other elements would be expressed or modified in a way that optimizes cell lodgment, function and survival in a particular location.

It is known that the different FABP isoforms have unique lipid specificity (38) and their expression is adapted to the available resources found in distinct locations throughout the body (22, 23). Whilst it was previously shown that FABP 4 and 5 are important for T_{RM} cell persistence in the skin (18), it remained unclear whether this was a general property of T_{RM} cells distributed throughout the body. Our results show that whilst FABP expression is a general feature of T_{RM} cells in a variety of different tissues, such expression is not limited to FABP 4 and 5. Moreover, our results employing FABP1 deletion in liver T_{RM} cells, when combined with those of Pan *et al.* (18) examining the effects of FABP4 and 5 elimination in the skin, argue that selective FABP expression is necessary for T_{RM} cell survival in the non-lymphoid compartment.

Diverse patterns of FABP expression occur in T_{RM} cells, which is linked to location of T cell lodgment and determined by factors present in the tissue. Further, selective FABP isoform expression is seen in other tissue-resident leukocytes such as ILC and tissue-resident myeloid cells, although some variation is seen such as the co-dominant expression of FABP5 only in liver NKT cells. Consequently, it appears that although FABP expression represents a common element in T_{RM} cell development, the specific form of its expression is inextricably tied to anatomical location within the body. Such specialization makes sense since FABP selection is likely optimized to the milieu in which cells reside, regardless of whether they are lymphoid, myeloid or parenchymal in origin.

The transcriptional program responsible for tissue residency has been described in much detail over recent years. This includes expression of master transcription factors such as Blimp-1 or its homologue Hobit that together modulate KLF2 and downstream elements such as S1P1 and CCR7, thus inhibiting T cell egress from the tissues (7, 13). Here, we find that factors associated with the tissue microenvironment overlays this fundamental control of tissue-residency, which in this case, fine-tune FABP usage to best fit the given site of T cell lodgment. It may be that the general tissue

residency program initiates FABP expression as T_{RM} cells mature in non-lymphoid tissues since, as we show here, this family of molecules is expressed by T_{RM} cells in a variety of different locations. Alternatively, since our results also show that factors unique to each tissue appear to induce the appropriate pattern of FABP selection, their expression may be dependent on mediators within the local environment rather than the residency program *per se*. Regardless, our results show that T_{RM} cells and other non-circulating lymphocytes are adapted to their particular tissue of residence, which is proposed to optimize uptake of fatty acids. This adaptation likely extends to other tissue-specific elements including some critical to T_{RM} cell retention or survival in a manner that is specific for their location of residence.

Materials and Methods

Mice, adoptive transfer, and infection

Six- to ten-week old female C57BL/6, B6.SJL-PtprcaPep3b/BoyJ (CD45.1), C57BL/6xB6.SJL-PtprcaPep3b/BoyJ (CD45.1.2), gBT-I.CD45.1, OT-I.CD45.1 and P14.CD45.1 mice were bred in the Department of Microbiology and Immunology, The University of Melbourne. All animal experiments were approved by The University of Melbourne Animal Ethics Committee. Naïve gBT-I T cells isolated from lymph nodes were transferred intravenously (i.v.) at 5×10^4 cells per recipient mouse followed by infection by skin scarification using 1×10^6 plaque-forming units (PFU) of HSV-1 KOS as described (2). Naïve P14 T cells were transferred i.v. at 5×10^4 cells per recipient followed by intraperitoneal (i.p.) infection with 2×10^5 PFU LCMV Armstrong. In some experiments, mice were shaved and depilated before treatment with 10 μ l 2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene (DNFB; Sigma-Aldrich) diluted at 0.25% in acetone:oil (4:1) on the skin 2 days after LCMV infection (25). For generation of mixed bone marrow (BM) chimeric mice, CD45.1⁺ mice were irradiated (2 x 550 Rads) and reconstituted by i.v. transfer of 2×10^7 BM cells from WT (CD45.1.2⁺) or FABP1^{-/-} (CD45.2⁺) mice at the ratio of 1:1. Ratio between donor compartments was assessed within the blood of recipients 8-12 weeks after reconstitution prior to infection. In adoptive transfer experiments of *in vitro* activated effector CD8⁺ WT (CD45.1.2⁺) and FABP1^{-/-} (CD45.1.2⁺) cells, recipient CD45.1⁺ mice received 1×10^6 cells i.v. followed by skin DNFB treatment.

Organ processing, flow cytometry, and antibodies

Spleens were processed through metal meshes into single cell suspensions. Skin tissue was incubated at 37°C for 90 min in dispase (Roche; 2.5 mg/ml) followed by separation of the dermis and epidermis. Dermis and epidermis were chopped into small fragments and incubated at 37°C for 30 min in collagenase III (Worthington; 3 mg mL⁻¹). Livers were processed through 70 µm meshes, and pellets resuspended in 35% isotonic Percoll (Sigma-Aldrich) followed by centrifugation at 500 g for 20 min at room temperature before red blood cell lysis was performed. Small intestines were removed of luminal contents and Peyer's patches, cut into 1-centimeter fragments and incubated at 37°C for 30 min with lateral rotation (230 rpm) in dithioerythritol (Sigma-Aldrich; 15 mg/ml) in 10% HBSS/HEPES. Cells were further separated using a 44/67% Percoll density gradient. Isolated cells were stained with the following antibodies and/or tetramers for flow cytometry or cell sorting: anti-CD45.1 (A20), -CD8α (53-6.7), -CD8β (YTS1 56.7.7), -CD3 (500A2), -Vα2 (B20.1), -CD44 (IM7), -CD45 (30-F11), -CD62L (MEL-14), -CD69 (H1.2F3), -CD103 (2E7), -CXCR6 (SA051D1), -Vγ3 (536), -CD11b (M1/70), -MHCII (M5.114.15.2), -EpCAM (G8.8), -NK1.1 (PK136), -NKp46 (29A1.4), -CD49a (HMa1), -CD49b (DX5), -TCRβ (H57-597), -TCRγδ (B1), -CX3CR1 (SA011F11), and -KLRG1 (2F1) from BD Biosciences or eBioscience. PBS57-loaded CD1d and H-2D^b/GP33 MHC I tetramers were obtained from the tetramer core facility of the NIH. Flow cytometry was performed on an LSR Fortessa and analyzed with Flowjo software (TreeStar).

Cell sorting and quantitative RT-qPCR

Lymphocytes were isolated from tissues and sorted into the following subsets using a FACSARIA III (BD Biosciences): spleen T_N (CD45.1⁺CD8α⁺Vα2⁺CD44⁻CD62L⁺CD69⁻), spleen T_{CM} (CD45.1⁺CD8α⁺Vα2⁺CD44⁺CD62L⁺CD69⁻), spleen T_{EM} (CD45.1⁺CD8α⁺Vα2⁺CD44⁺CD62L⁻CD69⁻), spleen T_{RM} (CD45.1⁺CD8α⁺Vα2⁺CD44⁺CD62L⁻CD69⁺), skin T_{RM} (CD45.1⁺CD3⁺Vα2⁺CD69⁺CD103⁺), skin ILC1 (CD3⁻NK1.1⁺NKp46⁺CD49a⁺), skin DETC (CD3⁺Vγ3⁺), skin LC (CD3⁻EpCAM⁺MHCII⁺CD11b⁺), liver T_{RM} (CD45.1⁺CD8α⁺Vα2⁺CD69⁺CXCR6⁺CD62L⁻), liver ILC1 (CD3⁻NK1.1⁺NKp46⁺CD49a⁺), liver cNK (CD3⁻NK1.1⁺NKp46⁺CD49a⁻CD49b⁺), liver NKT (CD3⁺CD1d-PBS57tetramer⁺), SI-IEL T_{RM} (P14 CD45.1⁺CD8α⁺Vα2⁺CD69⁺CD103⁺), SI-IEL ILC1 (CD3⁻NK1.1⁺NKp46⁺CD49a⁺), SI-

IEL TCR $\gamma\delta$ CD8 $\alpha\beta$ (CD69⁺CD103⁺TCR $\gamma\delta$ ⁺TCR β -CD8 α ⁺CD8 β ⁺), SI-IEL TCR $\gamma\delta$ CD8 $\alpha\alpha$ (CD69⁺CD103⁺TCR $\gamma\delta$ ⁺ TCR β -CD8 α ⁺CD8 β ⁻), SI-IEL TCR β CD8 $\alpha\alpha$ (CD69⁺CD103⁺TCR $\gamma\delta$ -TCR β ⁺CD8 α ⁺CD8 β ⁻) and SI-IEL TCR β CD8 $\alpha\beta$ (CD69⁺CD103⁺TCR $\gamma\delta$ -TCR β ⁺CD8 α ⁺CD8 β ⁺). RNA was isolated from sorted samples using a RNeasy Plus Micro Kit (Qiagen) and converted to complementary DNA using the High Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to manufacturer's instructions using a MJ Mini thermal cycler (Bio-Rad). Genes of interest were pre-amplified from cDNA using TaqMan PreAmp Master Mix (Thermo Fisher Scientific) on a MJ Mini thermal cycler (Bio-Rad) and samples were analyzed by real-time qPCR using a StepOnePlus Real-Time PCR System (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Taqman probes (Thermo Fisher Scientific) were used for all genes: *Tbp* Mm00446973_m1; *Hprt* Mm00446968_m1; *Fabp1* Mm00444340_m1; *Fabp2* Mm00433188_m1; *Fabp3* Mm02342495_m1; *Fabp4* Mm00445878_m1; *Fabp5* Mm00783731_s1; *Fabp6* Mm00434315_m1; *Fabp7* Mm00445225_m1; *Pmp2* Mm03015239_m1; *Fabp9* Mm0196433_s16. Cycle-threshold values were determined for genes individually and gene expression was normalized to the housekeeping genes *Tbp* or *Hprt* (Δ Ct) and presented as 2^{Δ Ct} (arbitrary units, AU). In heatmaps, *Fabp* isoform relative expression was normalized per row.

Transduction of CD8⁺ T cells

For transfections, 293T cells were seeded into 96 mm dishes at a density of 5×10^6 cells one day before transfection. Cells were transfected with Empty- or FABP1-pMSCV-Ametrine-encoding vector using CalPhos Mammalian Transfection Kit (Takara). Viral supernatant was harvested after 48 h by filtration (Millipore, 0.22 μ m) and 0.5 ml of fresh filtered virus supernatant transferred to 24-well plates coated with RetroNectin (Takara, 20 μ g/ml). Naïve CD8⁺ T cells from spleen and lymph nodes from naïve C57BL/6 (CD45.1.2⁺) or *Fabp1*^{-/-} (CD45.2⁺) mice were enriched and 1×10^6 cells were plated in 24-well plates (Thermo Fischer) pre-coated with anti-CD3 (clone 2C11) and anti-CD28 (37.51) (eBioscience, 5 μ g/ml). *In vitro* activated CD8⁺ T cells were transferred to 24-well plates containing viral supernatant and expanded for a further 3 days in the presence of IL-2 (Peprotech; 25 U/ml). Transduction efficacy was determined by Ametrine expression and 2.5×10^5 transduced WT and *Fabp1*^{-/-} cells were mixed 1:1 and transferred i.v. into C57BL/6 (CD45.1⁺) mice.

In vitro T cell activation and cell culture with organ supernatant

Naïve OT-I T cells isolated from lymph nodes were *in vitro* activated by OVA₂₅₇₋₂₆₄-pulsed target cells in the presence of IL-2 (Peprotech; 25 U/ml) as described (35). Effector cells were either transferred into mice (1×10^6 cells injected i.v.) or OT-I T cells were plated at 1×10^6 per well in 24-well plates and cultured with tissue supernatant. Tissue supernatants were generated from cell suspensions of spleen, skin or liver of naïve mice that were cultured in complete RPMI overnight at 37°C, 5% CO₂. The supernatant was then collected and spun down at 2000 rpm for 10 min to remove cells. Supernatant was added to *in vitro* activated OT-I T cells and incubated for 24 h. Cells were then collected for qPCR analysis.

Intravenous and epicutaneous liver T_{RM} cell transfer

Established populations of liver T_{RM} cells were sorted from LCMV-infected mice (30 d p.i.) and 1×10^5 cells were transferred i.v. into naïve recipient mice. Recipient mice were infected with LCMV and each side of the ear was treated with 10 µl of DNFB (0.25%) diluted in acetone/oil (4:1) to recruit transferred cells into the skin. Seven or 30 days later, transferred cells were sorted from various organs for qPCR analysis. For epicutaneous transfer experiments, liver T_{RM} cells from mice transferred with effector OT-I cells were sorted and transferred epicutaneously into naïve recipient mice as described (36). Briefly, recipients were anesthetized and the skin flank was shaved and depilated followed by abrasion with a power tool with grindstone attachment (Dremel) for 15 seconds with constant rotation. Liver T_{RM} cells were suspended in Matrigel basement membrane matrix (Corning) at 4×10^5 in 10 µl and applied to the scarified region. Mice were rested for 10 min to allow Matrigel solidification. The area was covered with Op-site Flexigrid (Smith and Nephew) and mice bandaged for 4 days.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed by one- or two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test followed by Bonferroni's post-test, by non-parametric ANOVA with Dunn's post-test or by Student's t-test when indicated in Prism 7 (Graphpad). P-values were represented by *, P < 0.05; **, P < 0.01; ***, P < 0.001; ****, P < 0.0001. Results represent mean ± s.e.m.

List of Supplementary Materials

Figure S1. Representative flow cytometric cell sorting gating strategies

Figure S2. Kinetics of FABP gene expression during T_{RM} cell development.

Figure S3. FABP protein expression in endogenous immune cells and liver T_{RM} cells.

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Acknowledgments

Funding: This work was supported by a Howard Hughes Medical Institute and Bill & Melinda Gates International Research Scholarship OPP1175796 to L.K.M and National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) APP1129711 to L.K.M. H.F. is supported by a National Science Foundation Graduate Research Fellowship and was supported by a National Science Foundation Graduate Research Opportunities Worldwide Fellowship. N.G.Z. is supported by FAPESP BEPE (2019/12431-2) Scholarship. S.L.P. is supported by a Cancer Council Victoria Postdoctoral Fellowship. H.M. is supported by an Australian Research Council (ARC) Discovery Early Career Researcher Award (DE170100575). J.A.V. is supported by an NHMRC Principal Research Fellowship (1154502) and Program Grant (1113293). L.K.M is a Senior Medical Research Fellow supported by the Sylvia and Charles Viertel Charitable Foundation. **Author contributions:** HF, RF, DF, SC, ME, NGZ, BvS and SP performed experiments. HF, RF, FRC and LKM designed experiments. HF and RF analyzed data. JV and HM provided supervision. HF, RF, FRC and LKM prepared the manuscript. LKM provided funding and led the research program. **Competing interests:** The authors declare no competing financial interests.

Figure Legends

Figure 1. Organ-specific expression of FABP isoforms in CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells. (A, B) Mice received naïve gBT-I.CD45.1 T cells and were subjected to HSV infection. gBT-I T cells were isolated from the skin 30 d p.i. and tracked based on expression of V α 2 and CD45.1. (A) Analysis of CD103 and CD69 expression by gBT-I T cells in skin. Data representative of three experiments with $n = 3-5$ mice. (B) *Fabp1-9* expression in gBT-I T cells sorted from the skin as analysed by qPCR. Data representative of two independent experiments, $n = 3-5$ mice each. (C, D) Mice received P14.CD45.1 T cells and were subjected to LCMV infection and were treated with DNFB. P14 T cells isolated at 30 d p.i. from the skin, SI-IEL and liver were tracked based on expression

of V α 2 and CD45.1. (C) Analysis of CD103, CD69 and CXCR6 expression by P14 T cells in skin, SI-IEL and liver. Data representative of two experiments with $n = 3-5$ mice each. (D) *Fabp1-9* expression of memory P14 T cells sorted from the spleen, skin, SI-IEL and liver or the spleen of naïve mice for naïve P14 T cells, as analysed by qPCR. (E) Heatmap of *Fabp1-9* expression in gBT-I T cells sorted from the skin and P14 T cells sorted from the skin, SI-IEL and liver. Heatmaps represent the relative expression of each *Fabp* isoform; with expression normalized within each sample row. In (A) and (B) numbers represent percentage of cells in the gate. In (B) and (D) bars represent the mean \pm s.e.m. and symbols represent individual mice. *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ANOVA with Dunn's post-test.

Figure 2. Kinetics of FABP gene expression during T_{RM} cell development. Mice received naïve P14.CD45.1 or gBT-I.CD45.1 T cells and were subjected to LCMV or HSV infection, respectively. P14 and gBT-I T cells were gated on V α 2⁺CD45.1⁺ cells. (A) Analysis of CD103, CD69 expression by P14 T cells in spleen and SI-IEL and gBT-I T cells in skin, and CD69, CXCR6 expression in P14 T cells in liver at 8, 14 and 30 d p.i. Data representative of two experiments with $n = 5$ mice. (B) Percentage of CD69⁺CD103⁺ gBT-I T cells isolated from the skin and P14 cells isolated from the SI-IEL and CD69⁺CXCR6⁺ P14 T cells isolated from the liver at 8, 14 and 30 d p.i. (C) qPCR analysis of FABP gene expression in CD69⁻CD103⁻CXCR6⁻ P14 T cells sorted from the spleen, CD69⁺CD103⁻ and CD69⁺CD103⁺ from SI-IEL, CD69⁻CXCR6⁻ and CD69⁺CXCR6⁺ from liver and CD69⁺CD103⁻ and CD69⁺CD103⁺ gBT-I T cells sorted from total skin or epidermis at 0, 7, 8, 14 and 30 d p.i. Data pooled from four independent experiments, $n = 5$ mice each. (D) Heatmap of FABP gene expression for gBT-I T cells isolated from the skin (CD69⁺CD103⁻ and CD69⁺CD103⁺), P14 T cells isolated from SI-IEL (CD69⁺CD103⁻ and CD69⁺CD103⁺) and liver (CD69⁻CXCR6⁻ and CD69⁺CXCR6⁺) at 8, 14 or 30 d p.i. as shown in (C). Heatmaps represent relative expression of *Fabp* isoforms within each sample. Symbols indicate mean \pm s.e.m.

Figure 3. FABP1-deficient T cells show impaired T_{RM} cell generation in the liver. (A-C) Naïve CD45.1⁺ mice were irradiated and received bone marrow cells from naïve wild-type (WT, CD45.1.2⁺) and *Fabp1*^{-/-} (CD45.2⁺) at a 1:1 ratio. Recipient mice were infected with LCMV and tissues were harvested 14 d p.i. LCMV-specific cells were tracked using tetramer. (A) Experimental schematic. (B) Quantification of WT and *Fabp1*^{-/-} CD8⁺ gp33⁺ T cells in the spleen,

and gp33⁺ T_{RM} cells from the spleen (CD69⁺), liver (CD69⁺CXCR6⁺) and SI-IEL (CD69⁺CD103⁺). Data are pooled from three independent experiments with $n = 3-5$ mice per group. (C-E) Naïve CD45.1⁺ mice received *in vitro* activated WT and *Fabp1*^{-/-} CD8⁺ T cells and were treated with DNFB on the skin flank. Cells were isolated 14 d post transfer. (C) Experimental schematic. (D) Quantification of transferred WT and *Fabp1*^{-/-} CD8⁺ T cells in the spleen, and T_{RM} cells from the spleen (CD69⁺), liver (CD69⁺CXCR6⁺) and skin (CD69⁺CD103⁺). (E) Ratio of transferred WT and *Fabp1*^{-/-} CD8⁺ T cells in the spleen and liver 14 d post transfer. Data are pooled from three independent experiments with $n = 3-5$ mice per group. (F) *In vitro* activated CD8⁺ T cells from WT (CD45.1.2⁺) and *Fabp1*^{-/-} (CD45.2⁺) mice were transduced with either *Fabp1*-Ametrine (*Fabp1*⁺) or Ametrine-empty (EV) retrovirus. WT and *Fabp1*^{-/-} cells transduced with EV were mixed at a 1:1 ratio, or WT and *Fabp1*^{-/-} cells transduced with *Fabp1*⁺ were mixed at a 1:1 ratio. Cells were transferred into naïve CD45.1⁺ mice. Shown is the ratio of transferred WT and *Fabp1*^{-/-} cells in the spleen and liver 14 d post transfer. The ratio of *Fabp1*^{-/-} to WT CD8⁺ or T_{RM} cell numbers in the spleen and liver was calculated for each individual mouse. $n = 10$ mice. In (B, D, E, F) bars represent the mean and symbols represent individual mice. *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ****P < 0.0001, Student's t-test

Figure 4. FABP expression by T_{RM} cells mirrors that of endogenous immune cells residing in the same organ. (A) *Fabp1-9* expression in ILC1, LC and DETC from the skin, ILC1, CD8 $\alpha\alpha$ TCR β , CD8 $\alpha\beta$ TCR β , CD8 $\alpha\alpha$ TCR $\gamma\delta$ and CD8 $\alpha\beta$ TCR $\gamma\delta$ cells from the SI-IEL and ILC1, cNK and NKT cells from the liver sorted from naïve mice as analysed by qPCR. Data from 4 independent experiments with 5 mice pooled each. (B) Heatmap of *Fabp1-9* expression in endogenous populations of naïve mice. Heatmaps represent relative expression of *Fabp* isoforms within each sample. Data from 3 independent experiments with 5 mice pooled each. Bars represent mean \pm s.e.m. *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ANOVA with Dunn's post-test.

Figure 5. Organ supernatant induces tissue-specific FABP expression in CD8⁺ T cells. (A-B) Liver, spleen and skin from naïve C57BL/6 mice were harvested and processed to single cell suspensions. Cells from each tissue were cultured overnight in complete RPMI media. Supernatant was collected and cultured with *in vitro* activated OT-I T cells for 24 h, which were then collected for qPCR. (A) Experimental schematic. (B) *Fabp1-9* expression in OT-I T cells cultured with

RPMI, spleen, liver or skin supernatant for 24 h. Data from four independent experiments with 2 replicates each. Bars represent the mean \pm s.e.m. and symbols represent individual mice. ****P < 0.0001, (B, C) ANOVA with Dunn's post-test.

Figure 6. T_{RM} cells modulate their FABP expression upon relocation to new microenvironments. (A-C) Naïve mice received P14.CD45.1 naïve T cells and were infected with LCMV. At 30 d p.i., liver T_{RM} cells (CD69⁺CXCR6⁺) were sorted and transferred i.v. into naïve recipients, followed by LCMV infection and treatment with DNFB in the skin. At 7 and 30 d post transfer, ex-liver T_{RM} cell P14 progeny was sorted from the spleen, skin, SI-IEL and liver for FABP expression assessment by qPCR. (A) Experimental schematic. (B) Ex-liver T_{RM} cell progeny was tracked based on expression of V α 2 and CD45.1 at 7 d p.i. from spleen, skin, SI-IEL and liver. Data representative of three independent experiments, *n* = 5 mice. (C) *Fabp1*, *Fabp2*, *Fabp4* and *Fabp6* expression analysed by qPCR in ex-liver T_{RM} cells isolated from spleen, skin, SI-IEL and liver at 7 and 30 d p.i. of recipient mice. Data pooled from 3 independent experiments with 5 mice each. (D-E) Effector OT-I T cells were transferred into recipient mice for T_{RM} cell seeding. At 30 d post transfer, liver OT-I T_{RM} cells were sorted and placed in the skin epidermis of naïve mice by epicutaneous transfer (skin tx). 7 d post transfer, ex-liver T_{RM} cells were sorted from the skin and FABP gene expression was assessed by qPCR. (D) Experimental schematic. (E) *Fabp1-9* expression of transferred liver T_{RM} cells or ex-liver T_{RM} cells sorted from the skin 7 d post transfer as analysed by qPCR. Data from 3 independent experiments with 5 mice pooled each. Bars represent mean \pm s.e.m. Symbols indicate mean. *P < 0.05, ***P < 0.001, two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's post-test.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Supplementary Materials**Supplementary Materials and Methods***Western blots*

Splenic CD8⁺ T cells, skin DETCs, liver T_{RM} cells, liver NK and NKT and SI-IEL CD8⁺ cells were sorted from naive C57BL/6 mice for endogenous populations. Liver CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells were obtained from mice that received effector OT-I T cells >30d prior. Whole spleen and heart single cell suspensions were used as negative and positive FABP3 controls respectively. Cells were lysed using a solution of 0.5% IGEPAL CA-630 (Sigma-Aldrich), 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.4), 5 mM MgCl₂ with Complete Protease Inhibitor Cocktail (Roche) for 30 min at 4°C. Nuclei was separated by centrifugation at 14,000 RPM x 10 min. Samples were denatured using Bolt LDS 4X (B0007) and DTT (1M), 1×10⁵ cells were used per well and protein separation was performed in 4-12% Bis-Tris precasted gels (Life Technologies). Proteins were transferred to nitrocellulose membranes using IBlot System (Life Technologies). Membranes were blocked with PBS-T (0.1% Tween) with 5% ECL Prime Blocking reagent (RPN418V) for 1h at RT. Primary antibodies were diluted at recommended concentration in blocking buffer and incubated overnight at 4°C. Secondary antibodies conjugated to HRP were diluted in blocking buffer and incubated at recommended concentration for 1h at RT. Membranes were washed three times for 10 min with PBS-T after every antibody step. Signal was developed using ECL Start or ECL Select Western Blotting Detection Reagent (GE Healthcare; RPN3243 or RPN2235) in an Amersham Imager 600 (GE Healthcare) machine. The following primary and secondary antibodies were used: goat anti-mouse FABP1 (1:400; AF1565; R&D Systems), goat anti-mouse FABP2 (1:200; AF1486; R&D Systems), rat anti-mouse FABP3 (1:1000; MAB1678; R&D Systems), goat anti-mouse FABP4 (1:800; AF1443; R&D Systems), goat anti-mouse FABP5 (1:400; AF1476; R&D Systems), rabbit anti-mouse FABP6 (1:50; PA5-50407; Invitrogen), mouse anti-mouse Actin (1:10000; 691001; MP Biomedicals), goat anti-rat IgG-HRP (1:2000; 7077; Cell Signaling Technology), donkey anti-rabbit IgG-HRP (1:2000; NA934; GE Healthcare), donkey anti-goat IgG-HRP (1:10000; ab97110; Abcam) and sheep anti-mouse IgG-HRP (1:2000; NA931; GE Healthcare).

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1

Figure S1. Representative flow cytometric cell sorting gating strategies. Organs were processed into single cell suspensions and sorted using a FACSARIA III. All populations are gated on live cells. **(A)** Naïve $CD8^+$ T cells from the spleen of P14 transgenic mice ($CD8\alpha^+ Va2^+ CD44^- CD62L^+ CD69^-$), **(B-E)** Naïve C57BL/6 mice received transgenic $CD45.1^+$ P14 or gBT-I cells

(i.v.) followed by infection with LCMV Armstrong with or without topical DNFB treatment or with HSV-1 KOS, respectively, as described in methods. Cells were analysed > 30 d p.i. Shown is (B) splenic T_{CM} (CD8 α ⁺ V α 2⁺ CD44⁺ CD62L⁺ CD69⁻), T_{EM} (CD8 α ⁺ V α 2⁺ CD44⁺ CD62L⁻ CD69⁻), and T_{RM} (CD8 α ⁺ V α 2⁺ CD44⁺ CD62L⁻ CD69⁺), (C) liver T_{RM} (CD8 α ⁺ V α 2⁺ CD44⁺ CD62L⁻ CD69⁺ CXCR6⁺) and (D) SI-IEL T_{RM} (CD8 α ⁺ V α 2⁺ CD44⁺ CD62L⁻ CD69⁺ CD103⁺) transgenic P14 cells from LCMV-infected mice, and (E) skin T_{RM} (CD3⁺ V α 2⁺ CD44⁺ CD62L⁻ CD69⁺ CD103⁺) gBT-I transgenic cells from HSV-infected mice. (F-H) Endogenous cell populations were sorted from naïve C57BL/6 mice. Shown is (F) skin LC cells (CD3⁻ V γ 3⁻ MHCII⁺ CD11b⁺ EpCAM⁺) and DETC (CD3⁺ V γ 3⁺), (G) liver ILC1 (CD3⁻ NK1.1⁺ NKp46⁺ CD49a⁺ CD49b⁻), NKT (CD3⁺ CD1d-PBS57tetramer⁺) and cNK (CD3⁻ NK1.1⁺ NKp46⁺ CD49a⁻ CD49b⁺) and (H) SI-IEL TCR $\gamma\delta$ CD8 $\alpha\beta$ (CD69⁺ CD103⁺ CD8 α ⁺ CD8 β ⁺ TCR $\gamma\delta$ ⁺ TCR β ⁻), TCR $\gamma\delta$ CD8 $\alpha\alpha$ (CD69⁺ CD103⁺ CD8 α ⁺ CD8 β ⁻ TCR $\gamma\delta$ ⁺ TCR β ⁻), TCR β CD8 $\alpha\alpha$ (CD69⁺ CD103⁺ CD8 α ⁺ CD8 β ⁻ TCR $\gamma\delta$ ⁻ TCR β ⁺) and TCR β CD8 $\alpha\beta$ (CD69⁺ CD103⁺ CD8 α ⁺ CD8 β ⁺ TCR $\gamma\delta$ ⁻ TCR β ⁺). Sorted cells were stored at -80°C until processed for qPCR or Western blot analysis.

Figure S2

Figure S2. Kinetics of FABP gene expression during T_{RM} cell development. Mice received naïve P14.CD45.1 or gBT-I.CD45.1 T cells and infected with LCMV or HSV, respectively. P14 and gBT-I T cells were gated on V α 2⁺CD45.1⁺ cells. qPCR analysis of FABP gene expression in CD69⁻CD103⁻CXCR6⁻ P14 T cells sorted from the spleen, CD69⁺CD103⁻ and CD69⁺CD103⁺ from SI-IEL, CD69⁻CXCR6⁻ and CD69⁺CXCR6⁺ from liver and CD69⁺CD103⁻ and CD69⁺CD103⁺ gBT-I T cells sorted from skin at 0, 7, 8, 14 and 30 d p.i. Data pooled from four independent experiments, *n* = 5 mice each. Symbols indicate mean \pm s.e.m.

Figure S3

Figure S3. FABP protein expression in endogenous populations and liver T_{RM} cells. Spleen CD8⁺ T cells (CD8⁺CD44⁺), skin DETCs (CD3⁺ V γ 3⁺), liver NK cells (CD3⁻ NK1.1⁺ NKp46⁺ CD49a⁺ CD49b⁺), liver NKT cells (CD3⁺ CD1d-PBS57tetramer⁺), SI-IEL (CD8⁺ CD69⁺ CD103⁺) were sorted from naïve C57BL/6 mice . Liver T_{RM} cells (CD45.1⁺ CD8 α ⁺ V α 2⁺ CD44⁺ CD62L⁻ CD69⁺ CXCR6⁺) were sorted from mice that received *in vitro* activated OT-I cells (i.v.) > 30 days prior. Whole spleen and heart cell suspensions were used as negative (Spleen -) and positive (Heart +) controls for FABP3. Cells were lysed, nuclei was separated and lysate was denatured. Protein separation was performed in 4-12% Bis-Tris precasted gels followed by transfer to nitrocellulose membranes. Membranes were blocked and incubated with primary antibodies against FABP1-6 or Actin overnight at 4°C. HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies were added to washed membranes for 1h at RT. Signal was developed using ECL Start or ECL Select Western Blotting Detection Reagent and gels were imaged on an Amersham Imager 600. Pooled samples from $n = 90$ mice.